

RRI2SCALE Guidebook

December 2022

RRI2SCALE

RESPONSIBLE RESEARCH & INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS AT REGIONAL SCALE

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 872526.

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PROJECT INFORMATION

TITLE	RRI2SCALE – Responsible Research and Innovation Ecosystems at Regional Scale for Intelligent Cities, Transport and Energy
START DATE	1 January 2020
DURATION	36 months
WEBSITE	https://rri2scale.eu/
COORDINATOR	AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA - Italy
PROJECT OVERVIEW	RRI2SCALE has designed a robust methodological approach to assist regional R&I governance systems to effectively and sustainably address their Regional Dilemmas. Techno-moral scenarios will be “tested” via JRC’s Scenario Exploration System and Regional Dialogues, forming the basis for elaborating Regional Agendas and Roadmaps towards the integration of RRI principles into territorial R&I design. All project results will form the RRI2SCALE Toolkit for replication by other territories.
CONSORTIUM	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. AGENZIA PER LA PROMOZIONE DELLA RICERCA EUROPEA https://www.apre.it/ 2. HOGSKULEN PA VESTLANDET https://www.hvl.no/ 3. UNIVERSITEIT MAASTRICHT https://www.maastrichtuniversity.nl/ 4. UNIVERSITEIT TWENTE https://www.utwente.nl/en/ 5. Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC https://qplan-intl.gr/ 6. RESEARCH AND INNOVATION MANAGEMENT GMBH https://www.research-and-innovation-management.com/ 7. WHITE RESEARCH SPRL https://white-research.eu/ 8. HORDALAND FYLKESKOMMUNE https://www.hordaland.no/ 9. PROVINCIE OVERIJSEL https://www.overijssel.nl/ 10. KRITI https://www.crete.gov.gr/ 11. AXENCIA GALEGA DE INNOVACION http://gain.xunta.gal/

Executive Summary

Local and regional policy-makers are often confronted with a dilemma. They are called to develop policies that spearhead economic growth in their territory while, in parallel, promoting inclusiveness and improving their citizens' quality of life. Finding a sweet spot between the two constitutes a real challenge (the so-called "**Regional dilemma**"). And it is even harder when policy design concerns technology sectors, e.g., policies that accommodate and promote smart cities* initiatives. Such technology sectors are fast-changing, and new sectoral developments (e.g., the adoption of new technologies) don't always have predictable consequences on society, the economy and the environment (the so-called "**Collingridge dilemma**").

The document at hand serves as a Guidebook to support policy-makers involving citizens in designing policies related to technology sectors. It proposes a **five-phase methodology**. The first phase (i.e., the preparation phase) includes reviewing the current R&I landscape, identifying regional dilemmas and exploiting potential collaborations with other regions. The second phase investigates emerging trends in the particular technology sector and develops techno-moral scenarios for the region's future. In the third phase, the scenarios are communicated to the wider public to validate their content. Also, key stakeholders and citizens experiment with the scenarios using a simulation tool called Scenario Exploration System. In the fourth phase for policy design, co-creating an agenda with specific goals and initiatives puts forth a commonly agreed course of action toward actively addressing the identified regional dilemmas. Finally, during the fifth phase, ongoing monitoring of the process allows on-spot improvements and a solid evaluation of the incurred impact on society, the economy and the environment.

The current document is directed to **policy-makers and policy advisors at all levels**, mainly at the local and regional levels ones. It is also directed to other project consortia interested in the RRI2SCALE approach. It can be used as a guide to implement the five-phase methodology or adopt particular incorporated tools, such as the Delphi method, the Scenario Exploration System, and the monitoring and evaluation framework. Within all sections of the current document, **real-life examples from the RRI2SCALE project** are provided, as well as hints & tips and suggestions for sources to which the reader can refer for further information.

We envision this Guidebook to inspire other regions and project consortia that wish to adopt the RRI2SCALE approach. Further information can be provided upon request by the Deliverable leader, [Q-Plan International Advisors P.C.](#) The online version of the Guidebook is available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7432567>.

* The terms 'intelligent' and 'smart' cities are used interchangeably in this document, as both refer to the broader socio-technical construct of technology-enabled urban development and innovation.

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1. Introduction

Local and regional policy-makers are often confronted with a dilemma. They are called to develop policies that spearhead economic growth in their territory while, in parallel, promoting inclusiveness and improving their citizens' quality of life. Recent developments in the global techno-social landscape have led to the realisation that finding a sweet spot between the two requires more "social", open and **collaborative governance models**. Involving businesses, academia and society in the policy-design process can contribute substantially to mobilising tacit knowledge, upscaling institutional capacity for regional and urban innovation and transformation, and securing ownership and sustainability of the introduced policies and measures.

As commonly known, involving citizens in decision-making is neither easy nor straightforward. And it becomes even more complicated when it concerns **policies related to technology sectors** (e.g., policies that accommodate and prepare for the digital transformation of the local or regional economy). In such cases, relying solely on citizens' current needs and preferences can be misleading. The fast-changing nature of digital technologies requires adopting a forward-looking perspective. Thus, involving the public in a future-forecasting exercise can be considered.

The document at hand serves as a guidebook to the above. In particular, it aims to support policy-makers to effectively involve citizens in designing policies related to technology sectors, such as smart cities, energy and transport. It proposes a five-phase methodology for preparing, running, and evaluating such a process. The proposed methodology is compatible with the principles of **Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)**.^{*} Thus, it can also serve as a first step (or a good practice) for institutionalising an inclusive approach to policy-making in the governance processes of a regional or local authority.

Section 2 provides an overview of the proposed methodology. **Sections 3-7** elaborate on each of the five phases, namely (i) Preparation, (ii) Looking ahead, (iii) Engagement and Awareness, (iv) Policy design, and (v) Monitoring and Evaluation. **Section 8** provides the main conclusions, while the **Annexes** include several materials to support future endeavours (the RRI2SCALE Toolkit).

The methodology proposed was implemented and **piloted in the RRI2SCALE project**. RRI2SCALE was a three-year Horizon 2020 SwafS project (Grant Agreement No 872526), running through 2020-2022, that seeks to embed RRI values in the policy-making processes of four European regions, namely Vestland (Norway), Overijssel (the Netherlands), Kriti (Greece) and Galicia (Spain). Within all sections of the current document, real-life examples from the RRI2SCALE project are provided, as well as hints & tips and suggestions for sources to which the reader can refer for further information. More information about RRI2SCALE can be found on [CORDIS](https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872526).

Important Info

^{*} The European Commission (EC) understands RRI as "an inclusive approach to research and innovation, to ensure that societal actors work together during the whole research and innovation process. It aims to better align both the process and the outcomes of research and innovation with the values, needs and expectations of European society". Source: Moghadam-Saman, S., et al. (2020). The Regional Dilemma: report on how EU regions integrate RRI in territorial R&I landscape. RRI2SCALE project. Available at <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872526/results>

2. Overall Approach

First, policy-makers need to select a technology sector, such as smart cities, energy or transport, where their targeted intervention is directed. Normally, this should be a sector (i) either of particular interest for the region; (ii) or about which new policies (or strategic plans) are currently being discussed; (iii) or about which another national or supranational development (e.g., European Commission policy) calls for regional/ local action.

After selecting a focus sector, the methodology to be followed includes five key phases:

1. **Preparation Phase: Prepare the Ground and Set Up a Team**
This phase includes setting up a skilled team of people to run the process. Their work starts by investigating the current landscape of policies, strategies, stakeholder views, and dilemmas to be addressed.
2. **Looking Ahead Phase: Develop Scenarios for the Future**
This phase includes identifying emerging trends in the focus sector and developing future plausible scenarios that depict the region’s future in a comprehensible narrative.
3. **Engagement and Awareness Phase: Validate and Simulate Scenarios**
This phase concerns the involvement of citizens in scenario validation to gather feedback and make adjustments to the scenarios. Then, key stakeholders and citizens experiment with the scenarios using a simulation tool called Scenario Exploration System.
4. **Policy Design Phase: Build Agenda and a Roadmap for Policy Changes**
This phase addresses the co-creation of an agenda with specific goals and initiatives and puts forth a commonly agreed course of action toward actively addressing the identified regional dilemmas. Also, a roadmap is configured to embed RRI into regional/ local policy-making.
5. **Monitoring and Evaluation Phase: Measure Performance and Impact**
This phase runs horizontally and includes the ongoing monitoring of the four previous phases. Also, it includes the evaluation and the assessment of the incurred impact on society, the economy and the environment.

Figure 1: Overview of the proposed methodology

The current document is directed to **policy-makers and advisors at all levels** in Europe, mainly at the local and regional ones. Such policy-makers can belong to any department of their organisation and be either civil servants or elected. They may be directors (or have another similar position) in their department or simply willing to act as change agents in their organisations. The uideobook can be used to implement the

Important

five-phase methodology or parts of it. Thus, it can also be used by stakeholders other than policy-makers, such as NGOs, citizen associations, or businesses that want to engage with a broad set of actors.

3. Preparation Phase: Prepare the Ground and Set Up a Team

Successful implementation starts with setting up a motivated and competent team. The team may consist of people working for the regional or local authority and be supported by external experts (advisors). Afterwards, the team needs to acquire some necessary background knowledge. In particular, the team needs to:

1. review the current landscape, including territorial innovation policies, political landscape and regional citizens' current views, attitudes and needs (section 3.1.);
2. identify regional dilemmas and consider examples of policies and initiatives to address them (section 3.2.);
3. collaborate with other regional or local authorities to develop synergies or exchange good practices (section 3.3.).

3.1. Review the current landscape

As a first step, reviewing and understanding the region's current situation and landscape is essential since any proposed policies should be compatible. For instance, the team may review the following:

- the economic landscape of the region, including key macroeconomic indicators, flourishing and innovative sectors, and regional competitive advantages;
- the political landscape in the region, including the governance structure (e.g., governor, councils and committees), the responsibilities and roles of the regional and local authorities, and key political parties;
- regional or urban innovation policies and strategies (such as the Smart Specialisation Strategy and its key pillars), innovation networks and funding schemes;
- any strategic plans and policies related to the sector of interest, such as energy and climate plans and their key provisions, regulatory authorities, national strategies and laws;
- the level and form of civil participation in the region. Examples include voting, volunteering, and participating in group activities.

Extensive desk research is required to gather the above information. Also, in-depth interviews or focus groups with the region's citizens and key stakeholders may need to be performed to complement desk research findings with hard-to-grasp and often fast-changing insights. Face-to-face interviews are suggested if the information is more sensitive and the stakeholders are reluctant to share. On the other hand, focus groups are highly recommended when the team wants to uncover dynamics, cleavages and convergences of opinions between citizens and stakeholders.

Afterwards, a deeper dive into citizens' and other regional stakeholders' current views, attitudes and needs is recommended. For instance, the team may perform an online survey to investigate the following:

- citizens' aspirations over the future trajectories of the region (e.g., should it be a hub of innovative small and medium-sized businesses or a highly-digitalised public sector region?);

- citizens' priorities for future public investment (e.g., the region should provide grants for research and innovation activities, developing skills or creating new public spaces?);
- citizens' moral views and preferences on trade-offs between promoting innovation and improving citizens' wellbeing (as well as promoting gender equality and safeguarding personal data and privacy);
- citizens' trust in local institutions (e.g., regional government, civil society organisations, research institutes and large corporations) and their attitudes towards public participation (e.g., past experiences, willingness to participate, and preferred methods).

A key strength of using an online survey is that the team can gather large-scale information that is anonymous, quantifiable, and easy to process. Also, it can discover how preferences, priorities and aspirations differ among societal groups (e.g., do women share the same opinion as men?; do private sector stakeholders have the same priorities as academic stakeholders?).

Examples of the above research can be found in the following documents:

- Moghadam-Saman, S., et al. (2020). The Regional Dilemma: report on how EU regions integrate RRI in territorial R&I landscape. RRI2SCALE project. Available at <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872526/results>
- Panori, A., et al. (2020). Large scale regional citizen surveys report. RRI2SCALE project. Available at <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872526/results>

A questionnaire that local or regional authorities can use to understand their citizens' views, attitudes and needs is available in [Annexe 1](#).

Resources

3.2. Identify regional dilemmas and good practices

The team should devise a list of current dilemmas in the region by combining the above knowledge and -potentially- after consulting local stakeholders. The dilemmas can be broad or apply specifically to the selected sector of interest. The later phases (i.e., looking ahead, engagement and policy design) will shed further light on the dilemmas and propose changes to policies or strategic plans that could contribute to addressing them.

Dilemmas are “situations in which a difficult choice has to be made between two or more alternatives” (Ribeiro et al., 2018). A typical dilemma is the trade-offs between ecology and economy (Paredes-Frigolett et al., 2015).¹

Definition

In RRI2SCALE, after research in local newspapers and news websites, and consultation with stakeholders, we identified key policy dilemmas in Vestland, Overijssel, Kriti and Galicia. Below, a description of one of Kriti's dilemmas is provided.

The dilemma in one sentence: To what extent should regional innovation policy promote mass, revenue-generating tourism at the expense of sustainable, place-based development and culture? Where is the 'sweet spot' between costs and benefits?

- **One side of the coin:** Tourism is critical to the local economy's success. Tourism and trade contribute to the local economy by a 35% share each. Also, cultural tourism constitutes one of the four pillars of the region's RIS3 strategy.

The RRI2SCALE example

- **The other side of the coin:** Mass tourism and over-tourism risk degrading historical heritage, the urban fabric, and the traditional bonds that bring together local communities over a shared identity. Moreover, they create significant sustainability risks related to public health concerns, lack of adequate public and open spaces, overuse of public infrastructure and traffic pollution.

Afterwards, the team can consider cases of other regions facing similar dilemmas. How did they capture what society wanted, how did they involve a wide range of stakeholders, how did they consider all possible impacts, and how did they manage to be open and transparent? Reviewing the difficulties and challenges those regions faced, the solutions adopted, the results achieved, and the lessons learned can help avoid similar mistakes and adopt best practices.

More examples of dilemmas that European regions face can be found in the document below:

- Dijkstra, A., et al. (2021). Techno-moral scenarios for territorial R&I futures in the domains of intelligent cities, energy and transport. RRI2SCALE project. Available at <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872526/results>

Examples of good practices undertaken in European regions to turn research and innovation more responsible are available in the following document:

- Fellnhöfer, K., et al. (2020). RRI integration: Final Good Practices Compendium. RRI2SCALE project. Available at <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872526/results>

Resources

3.3. Collaborate with other regional or local authorities

In addition to the above, the team can explore and exploit collaborations with other regions. The team could approach regions experienced in public participation and/ or regions facing similar dilemmas. Collaboration allows policy makers to address problems they would not be able to solve independently and benefit from synergies (e.g., by entering into shared services or procurement agreements with other regional or local authorities to provide critical services). The team could use their network of regions or contact existing networks, coalitions and associations of regions to find appropriate collaborators.

In RRI2SCALE, we organised a series of cross-regional dialogues to promote the development of cross-regional partnerships, exchange knowledge and experience, and enhance openness, transparency and engagement. Also, the four regions participating in the project, namely Vestland (Norway), Overijssel (the Netherlands), Kriti (Greece) and Galicia (Spain), signed a Memorandum of Collaboration to sustain collaboration in the longer run. They agreed to consider collaboration by various means, including but not limited to (i) joint events, seminars and workshops; (ii) joint awareness-raising campaigns; (iii) joint implementation of programmes and/ or projects; (iv) exchange of information and past experiences; (v) participation of experts in meetings; (vi) staff visits on a short-term basis for enhanced knowledge exchanges; and (vii) shared services or procurement agreements.

Finally, in RRI2SCALE, we resorted to a series of know-how exchanges with regional authorities and agencies from sister projects (i.e., projects that received funding under the same European Commission call). Under a spirit of mutual support, these synergies helped the four RRI2SCALE regions identify similar dilemmas that other regions were facing and potential solutions for regional policy-making that integrates the RRI principles. Mutual support was materialised in the form of exchanging relevant material (e.g.,

The RRI2SCALE example

policy briefs), organising virtual discussions in webinars, and holding roundtables in physical events (e.g., in the RRI2SCALE Final Conference).

The team could use the following network to find appropriate collaborators:

- The **European Committee of the Regions** (CoR) is the EU's assembly of local and regional representatives that provides sub-national authorities (i.e., regions, counties, provinces, municipalities and cities) with a direct voice within the EU's institutional framework. It is composed of 329 members and 329 alternates from all EU countries.

Other types of networks exist, such as ERRIN, the Vanguard Initiative, Eurocities, ICLEI, etc.

Resources

4. Looking Ahead Phase: Develop Scenarios for the Future

As a next step, the team needs to investigate future developments that may affect the region within the upcoming five to ten years. Such developments are generally of three types: (i) social, technological, economic and environmental megatrends; (ii) sectoral developments (pertinent to the selected sector of interest); and (iii) changes in people's views (including moral views, perceptions, needs and preferences). The current section elaborates on ways to anticipate each of these developments.

4.1. Identification of megatrends

Megatrends are macro-level (even global) phenomena that define the future by having a far-reaching impact on businesses, economies, industries, societies and individuals.^{2,3} They have been going on for many years and promise to last for a long time ahead.⁴

Definition

We suggest reviewing key megatrends in the social, technological, economic and environmental domains. Examples of megatrends can be population rise and ageing, urbanisation and migration, technological innovation and digital transition, potential recessions and power shifts, resource scarcity and climate change. Understanding those megatrends is a crucial first step to foreseeing the future of a region.

Reviewing relevant and most recent research and policy reports, scientific journal articles, and other scientific publications elaborated by international public and private institutions can provide an overview of the most-cited megatrends. The focus should be placed on how these megatrends can impact the life and work of people in the region. For example, the text should not focus on the various upgrades of the Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology but rather on the impact of AI technological products on employment (e.g., robotisation) and education (e.g., need for soft skills).

- Forecasting and planning for the future are regarded to be the basis for rational decision-making.⁵ Yet, the future is uncertain and most often unpredictable.^{6,7} Thus, forecasting studies should not be perceived as predictors of the future but rather as “tools to broadly describe the space within which actual futures are likely to develop”,⁸ helping all concerned parties to manage the uncertainty.⁹
- An important note is to investigate not only what takes place globally but also at the continent or national level (if possible). This is because often, megatrends may vary significantly among countries. For instance, the North European population is expected to grow by 4% by 2030, while the Southern Europe population is expected to decrease by 3%.¹⁰

In RRI2SCALE, we performed a similar review and identified twelve key megatrends. Below, the description of the technological megatrend “**Changing the Education Paradigm**” is provided.

“The digital transformation of our society brings in new ways of working and requires the possession of new knowledge and skills by workers.¹¹ In particular, the skills gap is already evident, with 40% of European employers facing difficulties finding employees with the proper skills to “grow and innovate” (2018).¹² Under this frame, education is progressively shifting from obtaining a degree to developing skills and specifically soft skills.^{13,14,*} The World Economic Forum classified: (i) analytical thinking and innovation; (ii) active learning and learning strategies; and (iii) creativity, originality and initiative as three of the most in-demand soft skills of 2022.¹⁵ In this respect, the importance of non-formal and informal learning (i.e., gained at work, through social activities, volunteering etc.), as well as lifelong learning, is increasing.^{16,†}

The influx of younger generations and the digitalisation of society induce changes not only in educational needs but also in the modes of delivery.¹⁷ An abundance of knowledge is becoming easily accessible by everyone on the internet, and online educational courses are gaining ground.¹⁸

4.2. Identification of sectoral developments

For the identification of developments in the selected sector of interest, several forecasting methods have been proposed since the early 1960s.¹⁹ Although performing a literature review similar to the above could suffice, the information required is often too specific to find in published sources. Thus, we suggest performing the Delphi method, which facilitates the development of reliable group opinions by providing diverse experts with a place to discuss within a structured setting.²⁰

The **Delphi method** is a multi-round expert survey in which, “in the second and later rounds of the survey, the results of the previous round are given as feedback”.²¹ More specifically, the Delphi method initiates an ordinary opinion survey to solicit experts’ opinions on a subject. What differentiates Delphi is that, afterwards, the facilitator collects, consolidates, and returns these opinions to the experts individually.

* Soft skills are character traits and interpersonal skills that characterize relationships with other people and complement hard skills in the workplace. Source: Kenton, W. (2020). Soft Skills. Investopedia. Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/s/soft-skills.asp>

† Informal education is the type of knowledge that one gains through several life experiences. Non-formal education is one that is framed according to the requirement of a particular job. Source: Globale, E. (2020). Types Of Education: Formal, Informal and Non-Formal. Medium. Retrieved from <https://medium.com/@ecoleglobale101/types-of-education-formal-informal-and-non-formal-ae0495004a9>

Then, during the second (and any later) round, the experts can revise their viewpoints under the influence of their colleagues' opinions.

A critical success factor for the Delphi method is the questionnaire quality. Building a valuable questionnaire begins with a literature review to understand the state of play in the sector and then decide on the most crucial information required for policy design. Such information can be phrased as projections of possible developments in one-sentence statements. Then, in the questionnaire, experts indicate their degree of agreement with each statement. An ordinal 5-point Likert-type response scale, ranging from "Firmly disagree" to "Firmly agree", can be used.

Moreover, a Delphi survey's outcome largely depends on the group of participants involved.²² A narrow set of criteria for selecting experts may "*lead to unrepresentative views or miss important sources of knowledge*".²³ Thus, the selected experts need to at least: (i) be aware of the current state of play in the sector of interest;²⁴ and (ii) have heterogeneous backgrounds (in terms of the type of stakeholder, nationality, etc.), as "*more diverse viewpoints reduce certain polarisation of preferences and responses*".²⁵

- The questionnaire statements need to meet certain quality criteria, such as (i) to be concise and avoid complexity which may lead to confusion; (ii) to focus on a single issue to avoid ambiguity; and (iii) to exclude positive or negative item wordings to avoid any influence on respondents.^{26,27}
- Participants can also be invited to provide comments (share arguments) for or against a statement. In doing so, the Delphi method can provide additional insights into the investigated topic and resolve the problem of lack of justification.²⁸
- Compliance with the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) or other relevant national laws may require participants' consent to handle their data and provide them with a privacy policy and a data subject request form.
- There is no optimum choice concerning the number of participants in a Delphi survey. It depends on the scope of the study, the desired panel diversity, and the availability of experts in the area under investigation.²⁹ There are Delphi studies featuring 18-40 participants^{30,31,32,33}, others with 73-76,^{34,35} but also others with 127 participants.³⁶

Hints & Tips

After completing the first round of the Delphi survey, results need to be analysed to check for consensus among participants. Following the paradigm of Dajani et al. (1979), the level of agreement between participants can be categorised based on the below decision rule:

- **Majority agreement** occurs when more than 70% of the respondents have stated that they either (i) agree/ firmly agree; or (ii) disagree/ firmly disagree. Such statements are perceived as highly probable to realise.
- **Majority disagreement** occurs when there is a preference over an opinion, but less than 70% of the experts support it.³⁷ Such statements are perceived as less probable to realise.
- **Bipolarity** occurs when respondents are equally divided over an issue (i.e., provided two conflicting forecasts). A convenient way to check for bipolarity, as proposed by Von Briel (2018), is to analyse the histogram of each statement. If the histogram has more than one peak, then bipolarity is present.³⁸

In the second round, as is common in Delphi surveys, the statements on topics where majority agreement has already been achieved can be omitted to minimise survey fatigue (McMillan et al., 2016). The iterative process theoretically ends once views have been stabilised, meaning that participants' responses no longer alter significantly between successive rounds of feedback.³⁹ Most current studies are limited to two rounds.⁴⁰

In RRI2SCALE, we performed a Delphi survey in November 2020. First, we investigated drivers of change, emerging trends and potential impacts in the smart cities, transport and energy domains. Then, we formulated 38 questionnaire statements and identified 954 experts as potential survey participants.

The following three statements are examples of potential future developments in the smart cities sector.

- **Driver.** The need to address growing urban challenges (e.g., increasing housing prices, traffic congestion, poor air quality, and urban flooding) will be one of the key drivers for European cities to pursue smart city projects.
- **Trends.** Local policy-makers in Europe will adopt an entrepreneurial mindset when designing smart city programmes and services (e.g., they will specify the services' value proposition, use smart procurement models and attribute importance to sustainability beyond funding).
- **Impact.** Smart city initiatives that will be undertaken in Europe will be designed in ways that consider the needs of vulnerable groups (such as the elderly and people with disabilities), improving the prospect of contributing to social inclusion significantly. Yet, these initiatives will be unequally uptaken across European countries.

The questionnaire was administered using the [Welphi](#) decision support system. There exist several online platforms (including open source software) that can be used to this end. Alternatively, a simple survey questionnaire could be administered, which, however, comes without the convenience of automatic analysis of responses.

During the first Delphi round, 120 experts provided their feedback (i.e., a 13.5% response rate). This feedback was collected, consolidated, and returned to the participants individually during the second round of the Delphi. At that time, participants had the opportunity to revise their responses based on other participants' views. A total of 88 valid replies were received, corresponding to a 73% response rate. The study outcomes indicate that majority agreement occurred in 18 out of 38 statements (16 statements in the first round and 2 statements in the second round); majority disagreement in 17 statements; and bipolarity in 3 statements.

Examples of performing the Delphi method are available in the following document:

- Angelidou, M., et al. (2020). Report on the identification of emerging territorial trends, drivers & potential impacts. RRI2SCALE project. Available at <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872526/results>
- von Briel, F. (2018). The future of omnichannel retail: A four-stage Delphi study. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 132, 217-229. Available at <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0040162518302026>

The questionnaire that can be used for a Delphi study on smart cities, transport and energy, developed in the context of RRI2SCALE, is available in [Annexe 2](#).

4.3. Development of techno-moral scenarios

On top of megatrends and sectoral developments that may affect the region within the following years, the team need to also consider changes in people's views, including morals, perceptions, needs and preferences. We suggest constructing techno-moral scenarios. Techno-moral scenarios help explore and clarify underlying reasons,

beliefs, values and concerns about new technologies. Also, they can be used in the “awareness and engagement” phase as a tool to stimulate imagination, reflection, debate, and public engagement.⁴¹

Future scenarios are “carefully constructed snapshots of the future and the possible ways a sector might develop”.⁴² Organisations usually create them to define key future uncertainties and discuss the impacts and responses they need to give for each one of them.⁴³ **Techno-moral scenarios**, in particular, highlight ‘soft’ impacts (Swierstra et al. 2009; Boenink et al. 2010), appraising how technologies may change ideas, values and ideals.⁴⁴

Definition

Constructing the scenarios begins by determining their structure. A popular way to do it is by selecting two of the most important drivers identified previously to use them as the axis of a matrix.⁴⁵ For each driver, two contrasting aspects are chosen to label the axis poles. According to Ringland (2002), three common areas of uncertainty are the following⁴⁶: (i) globalisation versus localisation; (ii) community values versus individual values; and (iii) quick adaption of new technology versus lagging adaption.

For instance, “social values” can be one axis, whereby one pole is labelled “individually dominated” and the other pole “community dominated”. Similarly, “technology” may be the other axis, whereby the poles are labelled “quick adaption” and “lagging adaption”. The result is four quadrants that provide the key structure for four different scenarios (see Figure 2). The first scenario would depict a region where the community feeling is dominant and the adaption to technology lags. The other scenarios are designed similarly.

The next step is writing the scenario text by considering and synthesising all previously gathered information from the “preparation” and the “looking ahead” phases.

The scenarios can be constructed as a narrative of about one page long, while the time horizon can be set to the next 5 or 10 or 20 years. Among general trends, it is important to explore the emotions and controversies that technologies and other developments may bring. The writer’s imagination is used whenever relevant literature or the Delphi findings do not suffice.

Figure 2: Matrix to support the identification of scenario structure

- Consider developing only two or three scenarios since citizens may find it challenging to grapple with multiple plausible futures.
- Consider adding one or two ‘wild cards’ into the scenarios. Wild cards are unexpected – yet plausible events with major consequences, such as natural disasters, social unrest, and demographic trends (e.g., due to disease). The purpose is to describe how resilient the region would be under those circumstances.

Hints & Tips

In RRI2SCALE, we used the findings from the Delphi survey and the investigation of the local landscape to create two techno-moral scenarios for each sector of interest (i.e., smart cities, transport and energy). The driver “regional innovation policy” was one axis, whereby one pole was labelled “flexible and adaptive design and implementation” and the other pole “rigid and intervening, top-down”. And the driver “citizen participation in regional decision-making” was the other axis, whereby the poles were labelled “High” and “Low”.

A summary of one of the RRI2SCALE scenarios is provided below. In particular, the scenario of flexible and adaptive design and implementation of the regional innovation policy and high citizen participation is presented.

“We are in the year 2031. The government has digitised most of its services. Local and regional administrations operate on the principles of smart governance. Thanks to large volumes of secure and anonymous data, they make the right decisions and respond quickly to the needs of citizens. For example, the region systematically monitors air quality and identifies the most polluted areas. In collaboration with the citizens of the areas, it selects targeted measures and interventions to improve its quality.

Governmental and Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) provide digital skills training and support in using digitised public services. They provide special programs for the elderly and immigrants. Citizens participate in open councils where they design and select innovative ideas that could be implemented in their region. When their ideas are good, the regional or local authorities implement them. Recently, for example, citizens made a detailed record of the bodies and organisations involved in the local circular economy. The regional authority used the recording and maps to improve its strategy since 2023.

Also, NGOs support social inclusion and social innovation. They emphasise the needs of the elderly and people with disabilities (PWDs). Much of their work with the various communities is done digitally. Most citizens are happy with their lives.”

More examples of future scenarios can be found here:

- Dijkstra, A., et al. (2021). Techno-moral scenarios for territorial R&I futures in the domains of intelligent cities, energy and transport. RRI2SCALE project. Available at <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872526/results>
- OECD. (2020). Back to the Future of Education: Four OECD Scenarios for Schooling, Educational Research and Innovation. OECD Publishing. Paris. Available at <https://espas.secure.europarl.europa.eu/orbis/sites/default/files/generated/document/en/178ef527-en.pdf>

[Annexe 3](#) provides a template to help local or regional authorities to structure and write their scenarios.

5. Engagement and Awareness Phase: Validate and Simulate Scenarios

The purpose of the “Engagement and Awareness Phase” is to stimulate the interest of local citizens, involve them in the whole process and prepare them (equip them) for fertile participation in the “Policy Design Phase”. In particular, local citizens are first called to validate the developed scenarios contributing to more realistic and

insightful content. Then they are invited to participate in a simulation session, enabling them to understand particular circumstances and trends in the region and develop a long-term perspective. For the simulation session, the team needs to prepare and set up the Scenario Exploration System (SES).

5.1. Validation of the techno-moral scenarios

Organisations typically want to validate their speculations about the future before committing to policy action. In other words, they want to ensure the scenarios' logical consistency and ability to serve as strategic insight and foresight tools.⁴⁷ One way to validate scenarios is to consider citizen perspectives, beliefs, and aspirations. In parallel, techno-moral scenarios can serve as a handy tool to raise awareness, engage the public, and feed the public discourse. For these purposes, we suggest organising a scenario validation process where local citizens can understand, discuss and potentially oppose the scenarios.⁴⁸ A scenario validation process can take place physically, in a workshop, or digitally using an online platform.

Scenarios are usually evaluated upon criteria such as plausibility, the difference from one another, completeness, and internal consistency.

- An option to communicate the scenarios to citizens is to turn them from text to videos. Consider selecting photos and background music that can be freely reproduced.
- One way to measure plausibility is to ask citizens: "How probable is this scenario to become a reality in your region within the next ten years?". If only a minority finds it impossible, then the criterion is satisfied.
- One way to measure the difference from one another is to ask citizens: "Which of the two scenarios would you prefer to become a reality in your region within the next ten years?". If the majority votes for one or the other scenario and only a minority states "No clear preference between the two scenarios", then the criterion is satisfied.
- Assessing a scenario in terms of completeness and internal consistency is slightly more challenging because a straightforward question (e.g., "What is missing from the two scenarios to be complete?") wouldn't work well. An alternative would be to pose a general question (e.g., "In what way would your life be affected if this scenario becomes a reality?") and allow people to leave comments. Then, from the comments received, you can elicit information on (i) any missing components from the scenario or (ii) any indications of flaws in the scenarios' internal consistency.

Hints & Tips

In RR12SCALE, we designed and implemented a validation process to assess whether the techno-moral scenarios developed meet high-quality scenario criteria.

First, videos presenting the scenarios were created (see examples [here](#) and [here](#)), uploaded on the RR12SCALE website and promoted through social media. Citizens from the four regions (i.e., Kriti, Galicia, Overijssel and Vestland) were asked to comment and discuss several aspects of the scenarios. They were also prompted to participate in a short survey, assigning scores to the scenarios' desirability and probability. According to Facebook statistics, our campaign reached more than 31,000 people, while we collected 386 comments and 279 valid survey replies.

The RR12SCALE example

In sequence, all the comments and replies received were analysed to identify recurring themes and assess whether the scenarios are plausible, different from one another, complete, and internally consistent, allowing us to make improvements.

Examples of scenario-building and validation processes can be found in the following documents:

- Angelidou, M., et al. (2021). Validation Report on Techno-Moral Scenarios. RRI2SCALE project. Available at <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872526/results>
- Kallis, G., Hatzilakou, D., Mexa, A., Coccossis, H., Svoronou, E., & Areos, P. (2006). Deliberative Visioning: A critical view Observations from a Scenario Workshop for water management in a Greek island. Available at <https://tinyurl.com/3ptf4esj>

Resources

5.2. Scenarios simulation

After validating the scenarios, we suggest inviting key stakeholders and citizens to dedicated sessions to experiment with the scenarios using a simulation tool. Such a learning process can help them understand better what the future may bring and, thus, be in a better position to participate in the following policy design phase. A useful tool to operate such sessions is the Scenario Exploration System (SES), which was adjusted by RRI2SCALE.

Stakeholder Exploration System is a role-playing board game that allows participants to experience and act through plausible alternative futures. The participants assume different stakeholder roles (e.g., policy-makers, academia, and business) and explore a universe different from theirs (e.g., a universe described by a future scenario). The aim is not to play a game and win but to promote a constructive conversation amongst key actors and long-term thinking in a spirit of collaboration.

Definition

SES was initially developed by the European Commission’s Joint Research Centre (JRC) EU Policy Lab to facilitate the practical use of scenarios in forecasting studies. RRI2SCALE adjusted the tool materials to accommodate a multi-stakeholder dialogue at the regional/ local level based on previously developed techno-moral scenarios. [Annexe 4](#) provides instructions on how to set up and operate the SES. Also, it provides examples of the materials that need to develop beforehand, such as the board and cards.

Figure 3: An example of the SES board

A critical factor for a successful SES session is inviting the right participants. We suggest inviting stakeholders who:

- have a stake in the innovation policy-making, domain of interest and/ or RRI within their regions;
- are regional stakeholders and could be both internal champions (within the regional or local authorities) or external stakeholders representing the quadruple helix;
- as a team, they are balanced in terms of age, career, gender and background; and

- can also participate in the agenda co-creation workshop. This is important because the knowledge and insights gained through the SES are critical to the policy design phase.

- At least one week before the session, consider sharing with the participants a supporting document with guidelines to familiarise them with information such as the purpose of the meeting, the SES, the other participants' and how the outcomes could be used.
- Experienced moderators are important for a smooth and fruitful session. We suggest organising several rehearsals to ensure that the team and the moderator are familiar with the SES.
- The success of the SES and its outcomes depend on good communication. Although digital sessions are safer in a pandemic and logistically easier to organise, physical sessions are much more effective and enjoyable. Also, digital sessions are significantly longer by default.
- Note-keeping during the session is important for the policy design phase. Expressed concerns about the region's future, other needs and preferences can serve as input to the agenda creation. Also, the moderator can elicit further information by directly asking relevant questions, such as "considering the various alternative scenarios, what would it be a realistic target for the region on the X topic?".

Hints & Tips

Additional instructions on how to set up and operate the SES are provided in the following materials:

- DesignLab. Instruction Video. Scenario Exploration System: Responsible Futuring. University of Twente. Available at: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1iduVre4tm7G5bWaMIFaMEASJYM6w1eKG/view>
- DesignLab. Quick Guide. Scenario Exploration System: Responsible Futuring. University of Twente. Available at: https://drive.google.com/file/d/1MSPCBefr8WKZh-Rz9_nFoNShWmSzuBN1/view
- van den Berg, M., et al. (2022). On the process and outcomes of the regional multistakeholder dialogues. RRI2SCALE project. Available at <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872526/results>

Resources

6. Policy Design Phase: Build Agenda and a Roadmap for Policy Changes

This phase's purpose is to use the knowledge generated in the previous phases and involve citizens in a participatory process to consider potential policy changes. We suggest organising two workshops, whose outcomes are: (i) an agenda to promote actions that address the regional dilemmas in the sector of interest; and (ii) a roadmap with steps for institutionalising an inclusive approach to policy-making in the governance processes of the regional/ local authority.

- **Agenda** is a planning tool to define specific goals and initiatives. It includes a clear diagnosis of the region's internal condition, a shared understanding of the goals, identification of the most critical opportunity areas, and knowledge of the capabilities, assets, and partnerships needed for success.⁴⁹
- A **roadmap** is a strategic plan that defines the desired outcomes and includes the major steps needed to reach them.⁵⁰

Definition

Before the first workshop, the team can synthesise (i) the background knowledge derived on the current situation and regional dilemmas from the “preparation phase”; (ii) the foreground knowledge gained through the forecasting studies of the “looking-ahead phase”; and (iii) the insights on citizens’ aspiration, preferences, fears and social roles from the “engagement and awareness phase”. Based on the above, the team can develop a solid suggestion for changes in the current regional/ local policies or a new policy that could contribute to addressing the regional dilemmas and is aligned with the principles of RRI. Also, it is recommended that the team invites the same stakeholders and citizens who participated in the SES session since the knowledge and insights gained through the simulation tool enable them to participate in the workshop more actively.

During the workshop, the team can briefly describe the current status and policy landscape in the sector of interest. Then, it may present its suggestions for policy changes and explain why and how such changes consider the estimated future developments in the sector and incorporate the views and preferences of citizens. Later, citizens can provide feedback, and a fertile dialogue may follow, discussing, among others, the shortcomings of the proposed changes and ideas to overcome those obstacles.

After the end of the first workshop, the team sets up the new regional/ local agenda pointing out the modifications needed in the existing or upcoming policies. Ideally, the team could disseminate the document to local citizens to receive feedback from a wider audience. Press releases, newsletters and a website or social media post can be helpful in this respect. Finally, the team forwards the agenda to higher-level policy-makers to consider adopting it.

But, regardless of the adoption of the agenda, the five-phases methodology proposed in this document can serve as a first step (or a good practice) for institutionalising an inclusive approach to policy-making in the governance processes of the regional or local authority. Thus, we suggest organising a second workshop with policy-makers and other stakeholders to discuss whether and how to sustain this practice for future-proof and participatory policy design. Also, this workshop could constitute an opportunity for discussing governance changes to embed additional RRI dimensions, such as gender equality, open access, science literacy and ethics. After the workshop, the team can prioritise the main steps and synthesise them into a roadmap for governance change. Finally, the team shares the roadmap with all the governance stakeholders, including those who might not have been present in the workshop but have an important role in or impact the governance framework.

Further inspiration for changes in the regional governance can be derived from the following documents:

- Moghadam Saman, S., et al. (2022). Agendas and Roadmaps of the RRI2SCALE Regions’ co – creation process. RRI2SCALE project. Available at <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872526/results>
- Willi, Y., Putz, M. and Muller, M. (2018). Towards a versatile and multidimensional framework to analyse regional governance. *Environment and Planning C: Politics and Space* 36(5): 775–795.

Resources

7. Monitoring and Evaluation Phase: Measure Performance and Impact

Monitoring the above phases and collecting data for assessment and evaluation offer many benefits. It can help the team:

- identify the strong and weak parts of their approach, infer any success and prohibiting factors and ultimately improve their way of working;
- understand the specificities of the region better, including regional strengths and weaknesses and thus, improve the team’s ongoing planning for the next phases of the process;
- collect evidence on the societal, scientific, economic and environmental impact of the whole process, then present it to policy-makers and other stakeholders and finally, gain their commitment to exploiting the results and supporting similar future initiatives; and
- provide themselves (i.e., the team members) with a sense of success or failure.

We suggest setting up a monitoring and evaluation framework following four steps:

- **First**, the team needs to decide on a list of objectives and sub-objectives for the whole process. For instance, the objectives can be to (i) address regional dilemmas in the sector of interest; and (ii) embed RRI dimensions in the regional governance framework. A few sub-objectives could be to (i) involve the public in policy design; (ii) prepare the region for upcoming developments in the sector of interest; and (iii) promote gender equality in the decision-making bodies.
- **Second**, the team needs to decide on the means to collect the required data and develop any relevant material. For instance, the team could ask the participants of the simulation session and the agenda workshop to fill in feedback questionnaires. Also, it could interview a few citizens. In any case, the team needs to develop the relevant questionnaires or interview forms, while abiding by all General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) provisions or other national laws. The team needs also to consider the questionnaire’s size, avoiding potential survey fatigue.
- **Third**, the team need to develop a list of indicators. The indicators need to, either directly or indirectly, measure progress towards the objectives and sub-objectives set. They can be (i) process indicators, which measure the quantity and quality of any actions taken and processes implemented; (ii) outcome indicators, which measure the tangible outcomes or perceived outcomes achieved; and (iii) perception indicators, which measure changes in the perception and values of the engaged citizens.
- **Fourth**, the team needs to collect the data and evaluate them. The first task includes calculating sums, mean or weighted averages, and trends. Then, based on previous experiences or expectations, the team can need to provide an evaluation of the data and come up with meaningful conclusions.

- Persuading workshop participants to fill in a feedback questionnaire is sometimes challenging. We suggest clearly explaining to them the purpose and the importance of collecting such data. Also, we recommend asking for feedback during or immediately after the event and not later.
- Evaluation of results can be made easier and more effective if target values are assigned to indicators. Target setting is an important tool for clarifying direction and assessing organisational progress. However, setting targets is not a trivial process. They should be SMART, meaning: (i) Specific (i.e., specific about what is to be accomplished); (ii) Measurable (i.e., to ensure that there are measurement methods available); (iii) Achievable (concerning the baseline situation identified previously); (iv) Relevant (i.e., relevant to the direction the process wants to go in), and (v) Time-bound (because targets without a timeframe may be forgotten or pushed to the side).⁵¹

Hints & Tips

Examples of relevant monitoring and evaluation frameworks can be found in the following document:

- Angelidou, M., et al. (2022). RRI2SCALE Indicators Database. RRI2SCALE project. Available at <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872526/results>

Also, [Annexe 5](#) provides a template to assist local and regional authorities in setting up their monitoring and evaluation framework.

In RRI2SCALE, we configured a list of more than 100 indicators. And we collected the necessary data in three ways: (i) we asked for participants' feedback after each participatory process (receiving more than 50 replies); (ii) we asked regional authorities to fill in a report every four months; and (iii) we regularly collected data from the Eurostat website. The key conclusions that we came up with as briefly provided below:

- The group of people in the discussions was sufficiently diverse to allow a meaningful conversation (76% of the citizens in the RRI2SCALE participatory activities agreed with this statement)
- The SES took place in a gender-equal environment (100%) and complied with research integrity standards (e.g., clarity in the research goals, respect for all participants and transparency in data collection methods) (88%);
- Participants had or were provided with sufficient background knowledge on the topics discussed to participate in the SES actively (82%) and gained a better understanding of potential developments, e.g., technological, demographical and economic developments (65%)
- Participants better understood the social role of various stakeholders (91%). However, only half of them improved their understanding of current dilemmas in their region (53%). Also, only a few of them said that, in the future, they would more actively search for information about controversial technologies (29%).
- Finally, in terms of perception change, they now think that analysing potential ethical issues must be an integral part of the strategic planning of the regional authority (100%) and consider new technologies as worth-investigating solutions to regional problems and challenges (64%).

8. Conclusions

More “social”, open and collaborative governance models are feasible and necessary to address regional dilemmas. Local and regional policy-makers can use the current document as a guidebook to involve citizens in policy design related to fast-changing technology sectors. In a nutshell, the guidebook proposes a five-phase methodology. The first phase (i.e., the preparation phase) includes reviewing the current R&I landscape, identifying regional dilemmas and exploiting potential collaborations with other regions. The second phase investigates emerging trends in the particular technology sector and develops techno-moral scenarios for the region's future. Afterwards, in the third phase, the scenarios are communicated to the wider public to validate their content. Also, key stakeholders and citizens experiment with the scenarios using a simulation tool called Scenario Exploration System. In the policy-design phase, co-creating an agenda with specific goals and initiatives puts forth a commonly agreed course of action toward actively addressing the identified regional dilemmas. And finally, ongoing monitoring of the process

allows on-spot improvements and a solid evaluation of the incurred impact on society, the economy and the environment.

The Guidebook and Moc summarise the legacy of the project and we envision them to provide inspiration for other regions and project consortia that wish to adopt the RRI2SCALE approach, or parts of it. Further information can be provided upon request by the Deliverable leader, [Q-Plan International Advisors P.C.](#)

Annexes (RRI2SCALE Toolkit)

Annexe 1 - Views, Attitudes and Needs Assessment Questionnaire

Annexe 1 provides a questionnaire that local or regional authorities can use to understand their citizens' views, attitudes and needs. It is also provided online at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7431738>

Welcome note

Dear participant, **welcome** to our survey!

The survey lasts **about 5 minutes**. There are no right or wrong answers. It is all about your views. All data is anonymised, and your privacy is guaranteed. Thank you very much in advance for your support, which is very much appreciated! If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact us via [\[insert the mail address of data collectors\]](#)

Best wishes,

The [\[name of regional project or initiative\]](#) team

[\[A one-paragraph brief description about the regional project or initiative can be added before the survey\]](#)

SECTION 0 — ELECTRONIC CONSENT

Before proceeding, we would like to kindly draw your attention to the following information:

PARTICIPATION

Your participation in this survey is voluntary. You may refuse to take part. Please be aware that if you do decide to participate, you may also stop participating at any time without penalty. There are 10 questions in this survey related to Responsible Research and Innovation, including processes or concerns in your region.

BENEFITS

You will receive no direct benefits from participating. However, your responses may help us to improve our work.

RISKS

There are no foreseeable risks involved in participating in this survey. By answering the questionnaire, you grant permission for the data generated from this questionnaire to be used **ONLY** for research purposes. The results will be disseminated in scientific publications and public reports wherein anonymity will be guaranteed. Regarding the dissemination plans, you can find more details via the following link [\[insert relevant link or website\]](#). Participants' utterances will be used in reports as quotes, but in such a way that anonymity is ensured. To sum up, any information provided remains ANONYMOUS!

CONFIDENTIALITY

Your survey answers and data will be stored in a password-protected electronic format. We do not collect any identifying information, such as your name, email address, or IP address. Therefore, your responses will remain anonymous. No one will be able to identify you or your answers, and no one will know whether you participated in the study.

CONTACT

If you have questions at any time about the study or the procedures, you may contact via email at [\[insert relevant mail address\]](#)

ELECTRONIC CONSENT

Please select your choice below.

Clicking on the "Agree" button indicates that:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ You have read the above information. ✓ You are clearly informed. ✓ You voluntarily agree to participate. ✓ Your anonymous answers can be used for research purposes. ✓ You are 18 years of age or older. 	<input type="checkbox"/> Agree
--	--------------------------------

Before starting, we would like to give you a simple definition of *innovation* that we use for this survey. More specifically, we refer to *innovation* as a set of new technologies and forms of organisation that reshape regional activities. It may include new digital services in various areas (e.g., transport or smart cities), as well as community activities that result in more effective collaborative actions (e.g., recycling or energy production).

SECTION 1 – IDENTIFICATION OF PRIORITY AREAS AND FUTURE TRAJECTORIES

In this section, we would like to get your views regarding the most important areas for investing in your region. This will help us provide regional authorities with a comprehensive list of priorities based on your preferences. The second question aims at identifying insights about your perceptions regarding the future trajectories of your region.

1. In the following list, please indicate which areas you would choose your region to spend money on.

	Low Priority	Medium Priority	High Priority
Provide grants for research and innovation activities			
Provide support to small and medium-sized businesses to develop and apply new technologies			
Support citizens and companies to use renewable energy sources by subsidising them			
Create new digital public services that are more easily accessed			

Upgrade transport facilities making them smarter and more efficient (rail, road, or airports)			
Skills development through vocational training activities			
Create new public spaces and infrastructures that serve regional specific social or environmental needs			
Other (Please specify: _____)			

2. In the long run, I believe that my region should be mainly shaped as (max two options):

- a hub of innovative small and medium-sized businesses that will attract highly skilled workers
- a highly-digitalised public sector region that uses citizen-friendly applications
- an energy-efficient region characterised by optimised energy production processes using renewable energy sources
- a high-mobility region that uses smart transport for optimising access, distances and time
- a high-quality-of-life region where citizens are heard and participate in addressing their daily life needs

SECTION 2 - POTENTIAL TRADE-OFFS BETWEEN INNOVATION AND RISING SOCIETAL CHALLENGES

In this section, we ask your opinion about potential conflicting aspects between innovation and rising societal challenges, such as negative environmental effects or exclusion of specific social groups from policy design processes.

3. Please indicate your agreement with the following arguments:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
I believe that promoting innovation should be a higher priority than citizens' well-being (such as jobs, income, housing, health, and safety).					
I believe that innovation should be boosted even though it might create gender inequalities in my region.					
I believe that it is good to support innovation when it has a positive impact on smart cities, energy, and transport, even if it requires access to my personal data.					
I believe that innovation outcomes for facilitating smart cities, energy and transport should be boosted, even if I might not have all the necessary skills to use them.					

SECTION 3 - TRUST TO LOCAL INSTITUTIONS AND PUBLIC PARTICIPATION

In this section, we want to explore general and institutional trust-related innovation, as well as your willingness to participate in regional innovation policy design processes.

4. In terms of general trust, I trust organizations or groups of people when they:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
assess the effects of innovation in an independent way					
look at the effects of innovation from different angles					
clearly indicate which interests they have in innovation					
communicate in an open way about innovation					

5. Please indicate to what extent you trust the following organisations in your region.

	Not at all	Not much	Indifferent	A little	Very much
Regional government					
Local government					
Civil society organisations					
Non-Governmental Organisations					
Researchers/scientists working for universities					
Small and medium businesses					
Large companies					
Gender balanced governing bodies					

6. Please indicate your agreement with the following arguments:

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Agree	Strongly agree
I believe that citizens should be actively involved in helping to design regional innovation policies					
I believe that citizens should be actively involved in helping to evaluate regional innovation policies					

7. Which of the following ways would you choose if you wanted to get involved in public dialogues? (max 2)

- individual direct communication (e.g., individual meetings, letters etc.)
- online channels (e.g., platforms, social media accounts etc.)
- formal working groups (online and live) representing a community or group
- open events organized by public authorities (e.g., workshops)
- Other (Please specify: _____)

8. Have you ever been involved in public dialogues?

- Yes
- No

9. To what extend are you willing to be involved in future public dialogues related to:

	Not at all	Yearly	Monthly	Weekly	Daily
smart cities					
transport					
energy					

SECTION 4 – BACKGROUND INFORMATION

10. Gender:

- Female
- Male
- Binary
- Prefer not to mention

11. Age group:

- 18 – 24 years old
- 25 – 34 years old
- 35 – 65 years old
- More than 65 years old

12. Please indicate your educational level:

- No or Primary education
- Secondary education
- Higher education (Bachelor’s degree or equivalent)
- Higher education (Master’s, PhD or equivalent)

13. Please indicate your activity status:

- Employed
- Unemployed
- Retired
- Student
- Household activities
- Other

14. You participate in this survey as part of:

- Academia or research
- Government
- Business
- Civil Society – General public

15. Do you have any additional comments you would like to include? (optional)

(Free text)

16. I want to be informed about the survey results (optional)

- Yes
- No

Contact email (please insert the email where you wish to receive our future updates): _____

- I do consent to receive newsletters and updates from [name of project, initiative, organisation].

Survey end

Thank you for taking part into this survey and contributing to our understanding of what people think about Responsible Research and Innovation! Your input will help us a great deal to identify key elements and perceptions that should be considered during the implementation of our project. Do you have any questions or comments? You can contact us at [insert relevant mail address]

Informed consent

[The survey should include an informed consent section so that the process is GDPR-compliant. Below is the informed consent that was used in the RRI2SCALE project survey, and it may serve as an example for future surveys]

This privacy policy details information collection practices related to your personal data and other related information and the limited manner in which the RRI2SCALE project will use and disclose the information provided to us when you responded to the survey.

By participating in the survey, you voluntarily consent to the collection and use of your information by RRI2SCALE as set forth in this privacy policy. If you have any questions concerning this privacy policy or our data collection practices, you may contact us at info@white-research.eu. We reserve the right to change this privacy policy at any time and inform all participants about the updates.

In addition to your opinion, we are collecting some personal information such as age, country of residence and educational status for socio-demographic purposes. The collected data will be saved and used until the end of the research period of the RRI2SCALE project. The data will be only used for the purpose of the RRI2SCALE, funded under the European Union Horizon 2020 program, aiming to promote Responsible Research and Innovation principles for Regional Innovation Policies across Europe.

The lawfulness of the processing of personal data is determined pursuant to Article 6 of the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). With respect to personal data, the processing of personal data is based on consent.

Annexe 2 - Delphi Survey Questionnaire

Annexe 2 provides a questionnaire that local or regional authorities can use to run a Delphi study on smart cities, transport and energy. It is also provided online at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7432013>

Clicking on the “I consent” button indicates that:

- You have read and understood the invitation e-mail sent to you and the purpose of this forward-looking exercise.
- You consent to your personal data being securely stored and retained for 1 year after the completion of the study, before ultimately being deleted by the consortium that collected this data.
- You consent to your personal data being processed by the online survey development software ‘Welphi’ based on the company’s privacy policy.
- You consent to anonymized quotations from your answers to be used in reports, publications, and publicly available outputs (e.g., infographics, etc.) of the study.
- You understand that you are free to withdraw your consent at any time without the need to justify your decision.
- You confirm that you have read and understood all the above and been given adequate time to consider your participation.

I consent

1. Based on your academic and/or professional background, how would you rate your level of expertise in the following fields?

Field	High	Moderate	Low	None
intelligent cities (e.g., data-driven governance)				
intelligent energy (e.g., smart grid, energy communities)				
intelligent transport (e.g., Intelligent Transport Systems)				
digital technologies and their societal impacts in general				
Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)				

2. You participate in this survey as member of:

- academia or research
- governmental body
- business
- civil society organization
- other (please specify)

3. Which is your country of residence?

[drop-down menu with all the EU-27 countries + “other” option and open box to indicate which “other” country they mean]

4. Are you based in any of the following European Regions?

- Vestland (Norway)
- Overijssel (the Netherlands)
- Kriti (Greece)
- Galicia (Spain)
- None of the above

Please state the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements in a time horizon of 10 years from today.

	Firmly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Firmly Agree
1. The need to address growing urban challenges (e.g. increasing housing prices, traffic congestion, poor air quality, and urban flooding) will be one of the key drivers for European cities to pursue smart city projects (in the areas of governance, energy, transport, health, etc.) in the next decade.					
2. Territorial phenomena that jeopardize environmental, social and economic sustainability (e.g., urban sprawl, overurbanization and uncontrolled urban development) will be the key driver for European cities to pursue smart city projects (in the areas of governance, energy, transport, health, etc.).					
3. Policymakers at both European and national level will support the design and implementation of local smart city initiatives through relevant policies and funding schemes.					
4. The technological advancements that will happen in areas such as the Internet of Things (IoT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) will improve the efficiency of smart city projects, making the prospect of smart city development even more attractive to European cities.					
5. Local policymakers in Europe will design innovation strategies that are more citizen-centric, rather than technology-driven and hence, they will prioritize initiatives that focus on the needs and preferences of citizens.					
6. Citizens in Europe will be increasingly motivated to co-design and co-implement intelligent city solutions and participate in public discussions about their deployment in their city.					
7. Local policymakers in Europe will adopt an entrepreneurial mindset when designing smart city programs and services (i.e. specify the services' value proposition, use smart procurement models and attribute importance to sustainability beyond funding).					
8. In their quest to adopt more financially viable and sustainable business models for their smart city projects, many European cities will encourage investment from the private sector.					
9. The outsourcing of smart city services and the adoption of business-like practices by European local administrations will undermine the importance of social and environmental					

benefits for society, in favor of economic benefits and efficiency gains.					
10. The market of technology vendors in the smart city domain will become highly concentrated by 2030, restricting the bargaining power of European cities and resulting to 'technology lock-in' phenomena.					
11. Ethical concerns associated with the use of intelligent technologies (e.g. the "moral values" of self-driving cars) will grow in importance and urgency in Europe and will drive the smart city solutions market.					
12. Privacy, security, safety, and ethical concerns will increase the reluctance of citizens to adopt new technologies, slowing down the uptake and proliferation of intelligent city initiatives.					
13. European regulatory frameworks will adapt to regulate privacy, security, safety, and ethical issues that arise due to the advent of intelligent technologies. Yet, national regulatory frameworks will adapt to these at an unequal pace across all EU-27 countries.					
14. Intelligent city initiatives that will be undertaken in Europe will be designed in ways that consider the needs of vulnerable groups (such as the elderly and people with disabilities) improving the prospect to contribute to social inclusion significantly. Yet, these initiatives will be unequally uptaken across European countries.					
15. Due to the deployment of intelligent city initiatives, socio-spatial segregation within European cities within the next decade will increase. More specifically, quality of life in certain urbanized areas will improve thanks to new technologies; in sequence, the cost of housing will rise; eventually lower-income populations will be displaced to other parts of the cities (the so-called "gentrification" phenomenon).					
16. Intelligent technologies within the next decade will have a negative net impact on employment in Europe, due to automation and large adoption/promotion of the gig economy (the so-called "uberisation").					

Please state the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements in a time horizon of 10 years from today.

	Firmly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Firmly Agree
1. Public transport authorities and operators in Europe will mainly use intelligent technologies to develop more cost-effective solutions for the delivery of public transport services.					
2. The number of either semi- or fully autonomous vehicles by 2030 will not increase significantly in Europe, due to public concerns regarding their safety.					
3. Intelligent technologies will be transforming travel via public means of transport (bus, trains) from "waste" travel time to "bonus" time in Europe. For instance, thanks to high-speed and					

seamless wireless connectivity, commuters will have the opportunity to work during their commuting time.					
4. The expansion of seamless connectivity and interoperability in digital services in European cities will further promote shared mobility solutions (e.g., ridesharing, carsharing and bike-sharing).					
5. The expansion of seamless connectivity and interoperability in digital services in European cities will urge the evolution of micro mobility (e.g. bicycles, scooters, electric skateboards).					
6. The adoption of intelligent transport solutions will sharpen regional inequalities, as advanced regions with the necessary resources (infrastructures, financial capacity, etc.) will outpace the less developed ones.					
7. The use of Big Data and Artificial Intelligence (AI) will significantly contribute in the development and uptake of interconnected on-demand public transport in the next decade at regional level, also improving the connectivity between urban and rural areas across Europe.					

Please state the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements in a time horizon of 10 years from today.

	Firmly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Firmly Agree
1. Public transport authorities and operators in Europe will mainly use intelligent technologies to develop more cost-effective solutions for the delivery of public transport services.					
2. The number of either semi- or fully autonomous vehicles by 2030 will not increase significantly in Europe, due to public concerns regarding their safety.					
3. Intelligent technologies will be transforming travel via public means of transport (bus, trains) from “waste” travel time to “bonus” time in Europe. For instance, thanks to high-speed and seamless wireless connectivity, commuters will have the opportunity to work during their commuting time.					
4. The expansion of seamless connectivity and interoperability in digital services in European cities will further promote shared mobility solutions (e.g., ridesharing, carsharing and bike-sharing).					
5. The expansion of seamless connectivity and interoperability in digital services in European cities will urge the evolution of micro mobility (e.g. bicycles, scooters, electric skateboards).					
6. The adoption of intelligent transport solutions will sharpen regional inequalities, as advanced regions with the necessary resources (infrastructures, financial capacity, etc.) will outpace the less developed ones.					
7. The use of Big Data and Artificial Intelligence (AI) will significantly contribute in the development and uptake of interconnected on-demand public transport in the next decade					

at regional level, also improving the connectivity between urban and rural areas across Europe.					
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Please state the extent to which you agree or disagree with the following statements in a time horizon of 10 years from today.

	Firmly disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Firmly Agree
1. The energy system transition will be pursued mainly by adapting and repurposing existing organizations and infrastructures and not replacing them with new ones. To this end, intelligent technologies will be introduced in the energy domain without fundamentally disrupting or rescaling system operation and ownership.					
2. Digitalization and smaller-scale generation and storage will drive a rescaling and decentralization of the system, both technically and institutionally, with regional and city/local authorities becoming key energy strategists.					
3. By 2030 the number of energy prosumers (i.e. individuals that both produce and consume energy) will significantly increase in Europe.					
4. The number of energy communities (i.e. communities that engage in collective energy actions guided by open and democratic participation and governance) will significantly increase in Europe.					
5. The adoption of intelligent energy solutions in Europe will significantly decrease the cost of electricity for households and businesses.					
6. Currently, the existing grid and the existing fossil fuel system are used to back up supply when energy from renewables is not available. This will continue being the norm in the next decade.					
7. Energy consumption can be expected to fall in the coming decade, due to remote working and digitized business operations, supported by sustained energy conservation measures.					
8. The need to analyze demand and adjust how much power is drawn and from where across the distributed grids will drive the advancement of intelligent technologies such as predictive AI, machine learning, IoT and blockchain.					

Annexe 3 - Scenario Building and Validation Tool

Annexe 3 provides a template that local or regional authorities can use to structure and write their technological scenarios. It is also provided online at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7432123>

Writing the scenario text requires considering and synthesising all previously gathered information from the “preparation” and the “looking ahead” phases. The scenarios can be:

- Predictive, where the most rigorous scientific findings are employed to estimate “what will happen”;
- Exploratory, where the various drivers and trends are examined to estimate “what can happen”; and
- Normative, where potential actions to achieve a desirable future are presented.

We suggest developing exploratory scenarios, explaining what may change regarding policy, technology, economy, society and environment. We acknowledge that writing the scenario text is a less structured process than the Delphi method and often relies on the imagination and creativity of the writer. So, the following table may help in this respect.

Table 1: Parameters for the scenarios

	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3	Scenario 4
General intro (+/- 50 words)	It is 2031...	It is 2031...	It is 2031...	It is 2031...
Society (+/- 100 words)				
Economy (+/- 100 words)				
Technology (+/- 100 words)				
Environment (+/- 100 words)				
Policy (+/- 100 words)				

After the development, validation follows. Here the reader may find more information on a few criteria commonly used to evaluate the scenarios. In particular, scenarios need to be:

1. **Plausible.** Scenarios are stories which, in some cases, may be exaggerated but are still not impossible. If scenarios are viewed as impossible or not feasible, they have to be rejected because they do not serve as a basis for discussion.⁵²
2. **Different from one another.** Scenarios must offer purposefully divergent versions of the future and must not overlap.^{53,54} Overall, developing scenarios requires the identification of the two most critical uncertainties (or drivers) in the topic of concern. But, if the two uncertainties act as proxies for one another, despite belonging to different conceptual categories, you would end up with similar stories.⁵⁵
3. **Complete.** Scenarios do not provide precise details, leaving space for the reader to add them.⁵⁶ However, it is important to ensure that no critical uncertainty (i.e., an uncertainty that does not subsume or act as a proxy for the primary axis drivers) has been overlooked.⁵⁷
4. **Internally consistent.** Scenarios must be internally consistent, without contradictions in the scenario logic or the scenario outcomes. It is critical to remember that scenarios must describe what could happen and not what would be nice to happen.⁵⁸

Annexe 4 – SES Instructions and Materials

Annexe 4 provides instructions on how to set up and operate the SES. Also, it provides examples of the materials that need to develop beforehand, such as the board and cards. It is also provided online at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7432023>

Before the session begins, the people are asked to undertake a role, describe it and define their long-term objectives. There are four roles: policy-maker, business, civil society organisation and academia (hereinafter referred to as “participants”). Also, there is one observer (hereinafter referred to as “public voice”). A brief description of each role is provided below:

- **Policy-maker.** A key public or political administration actor responsible for decision-making and implementation in the topic being explored (i.e., the domain of interest or the regional dilemma).
- **Business.** The representative of a business with meaningful involvement and/ or stake in the topic under discussion. It can be a large or multinational company with an influential role or a small- to medium-sized business with some local influence.
- **Civil Society Organisation.** The representative of a civil society organisation which undertakes activities influencing decision-making and/ or public opinion.
- **Academia.** The representative of a local university, faculty or laboratory that produces research relevant to the theme and can influence decision-making and/ or public opinion.
- **The Public Voice.** A substantial group of citizens and voters.

In each session, participants explore two contradicting scenarios (e.g., a positive and a negative scenario) during three time horizons in the future (e.g., 2021, 2026, and 2031). The board is divided into two areas, one on the left and one on the right part of the board, each dedicated to one scenario. In each such area, the three semi-circles represent the three time horizons (see Figure 4). Each session includes seven steps.

Step 1 - The session begins with the first scenario at the first time horizon. The moderator introduces participants to the “new world” where they have been placed. In particular, the moderator reads the megatrend cards and one scenario detail card. The **megatrend cards** describe worldwide, long-term trends that apply to both scenarios and all three time horizons. The **scenario detail cards** are six, each containing information on trends and events taking place in a particular time horizon (see Figure 6).

Step 2 – Each participant receives a few **action cards** with examples of actions they can take. They pick a card based on the information provided to them previously and their priorities and place the card on the board in the semi-circle corresponding to the relevant time horizon. Also, each participant has the option to pick a **real-life card** and follow the instructions written there.

Step 3 - At the same time, participants are invited to put **resource tokens** on their action cards. The number of resource tokens available to each participant for all time horizons is provided by the **scenario disk**. Allocating resource tokens to an action card approximates investing in that action and signifies how supportive the participant is of that action.

Figure 4: Example of an SES board

Step 4 – Once all four participants have taken action, the public voice can choose to support or rebel against them. In particular, the public voice holds several **special resource tokens** (see Figure 6), which it attributes to the action cards he/ she likes the most.

Step 5 – After all, the moderator creates a wrap-up story and calculates each participant's **score**. The scores are calculated by multiplying the number of resources allocated to each action card by the number of special tokens attributed to that card by the public voice.

Step 6 – Participants proceed to the second time horizon, where all the above steps repeat. What is different now is that participants can **collaborate**. In particular, participants can place a few of their resource tokens on other participants' cards. In this case, the score of the original owner of the action card is calculated considering the sum of all resource tokens. The score of the other partner is calculated considering only the resource tokens that he/ she invested in that card. The third time horizon takes place in a manner identical to the second time horizon.

Step 7 - At the end, the moderator summarises what happened under the first scenario and calculates the final scores. Also, the moderator asks participants to assess how well they have reached their long-term objectives and how close the participants' actions have brought them to a sustainable future. Finally, all the above steps repeat for the second scenario.

The whole session usually takes about 3 to 4 hours to complete. Figure 5 shows how the board would look after completing the first scenario. Also, Figure 6 shows several of the material required. The SES depends heavily on the scenarios used. Thus, any materials from previous SES, such as scenario detail cards, can not be used as-is.

The team needs to devote time and resources to adapting the SES to the region’s specificities and the scenarios’ content.

Figure 5: Example of how the board would look after completing the first scenario

Figure 6: SES material, including (1) a scenario detail card; (2) a megatrend card; (3) an action card; (4) a scenario disk; (5) a real-life card; (6) a special resource token; and (7) a resource token.

In addition, RRI2SCALE created a shorter version of the SES, without tokens and shorter time horizons. The board is provided below. It can be used when participants have less than 3-4 hours available.

Figure 7: Example of the shorter SES board

Annexe 5 – Monitoring and Evaluation Framework Tool

Annexe 5 provides a template to assist local and regional authorities in setting up their monitoring and evaluation framework. It is also provided online at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7432206>

Complete the following fields to set the building blocks of your monitoring and evaluation system.

OBJECTIVES Which are the objectives and subobjectives that you aim to achieve with the whole process?

For instance, an objective can be to embed RRI in the regional governance framework. A few sub-objectives could be to (i) involve the public in decision-making; and (ii) promote science literacy.

Objective#1 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Subobjective#1.1: • Subobjective#1.2: • Subobjective#1.3:
--

MEANS Which are the best opportunities to collect feedback, and which are the most appropriate ways?

For instance, the SES session and the agenda workshop may constitute good opportunities to gather citizens' feedback. The most appropriate means range from questionnaires to interviews and focus groups.

Opportunity#1:..... Mean#1:.....	Opportunity#2:..... Mean#2:.....	Opportunity#3:..... Mean#3:.....
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INDICATORS Which indicators need to be monitored to measure progress towards each subobjective?

Assign a few indicators to each subobjective. Some indicators may measure the quality of the process (e.g., the quality of the discussion in a workshop), the importance of outcomes (e.g., the popularity of policy recommendations) or the change in peoples' perceptions (e.g., their attitude towards participatory processes). Also, decide which opportunity should be exploited to measure each indicator. Finally, assign a unique identifier (e.g., O1.1P#1) to each indicator.

Subobjective#1.1			
O1.1P#1	process	<i>E.g., Number of citizens believing that the group of people who participated in the discussion was adequately diverse to guarantee a transdisciplinary approach and allow a meaningful discussion / Total number of citizens surveyed</i>	Opport#1
...	outcome		...
...	perception		...
Subobjective#1.2			
...	process		...
.....			

EXAMPLES The following table provides examples of potential indicators.

#	Indicator
1	Number of policy-makers who reported that their participation in the SES session contributed to appreciating the positions of different citizens / Total number of policy-makers surveyed

2	Number of policy-makers who reported that their participation helped them to understand potential developments (e.g., technological, demographical and economic developments) that could affect their region by 2022 and beyond / Total number of policy-makers surveyed
3	Number of policy-makers who reported a better understanding of the importance of considering ethics and social values as a measure to achieve higher acceptance of R&I-related public policies / Total number of policy-makers surveyed
4	Number of citizens who reported that their participation helped them to understand current dilemmas in their region better / Total number of citizens surveyed
5	Number of citizens believing that the group of people who participated in the discussion was adequately diverse to guarantee a transdisciplinary approach and allow a meaningful discussion / Total number of citizens surveyed
6	Number of citizens who reported that they had sufficient background knowledge on the topics discussed to be able to participate in the discussion actively / Total number of citizens surveyed
7	Number of citizens who reported that the structure and the facilitation of the workshops allowed productive interactions between all participants and stimulated public debate / Total number of citizens surveyed
8	Number of citizens who reported that their opinions, values and expectations had a significant impact on the developed agendas and roadmaps / Total number of citizens surveyed
9	Number of citizens who reported that their participation helped them to increase their trust in regional or local authorities / Total number of citizens surveyed
10	Number of citizens who reported that in the future they would more actively take part in participatory processes for policy-making or R&I design / Total number of citizens surveyed
11	Number of citizens who reported that the workshops were a gender-equal environment / Total number of citizens surveyed
12	Number of citizens believing that the developed agenda adequately promotes an equal representation of female researchers in the decision-making bodies and/or research-performing organisations / Total number of citizens surveyed
13	Number of citizens believing that the developed agenda will contribute to the adoption of new technologies by local governments as a measure to improve their relationship with the citizens they serve / Total number of citizens surveyed
14	Number of citizens believing that the developed agenda will increase the social approval and adoption of new smart technologies by embodying ethical standards to their design / Total number of citizens surveyed
15	Number of citizens believing that the developed agenda, if materialise, will promote economic growth and spread its fruits fairly across society / Total number of citizens surveyed

RESOURCES Who should you involve in the monitoring activities and what other resources do you need?

Should the people organizing the workshops also be responsible for collecting feedback, or should there be another dedicated team? Would the questionnaires be in paper or digital form? In the latter case, do you need a survey tool? Also, should the collected data be stored in a reporting database?

Team:

Other Resources:

TIMELINE Summarise your key next actions into a timeline to ensure smooth implementation

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